

A STRUCTURE-INTEGRATED NANOCOMPOSITE SENSOR SYSTEM CAPABLE OF SIMULTANEOUS MEASUREMENT OF OMNIDIRECTIONAL STRAIN AND TEMPERATURE

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ABSTRACT

Strain-based structural health monitoring (SHM) is essential for composite structures due to their complex and unpredictable failure mechanism. However, conventional strain sensors are inherently limited by their unidirectional sensitivity and their inability to distinguish strain from temperature effects without additional sensors, leading to complex configurations and extensive wiring. To address these challenges, a carbon nanotube (CNT)-based omnidirectional sensing system was developed, designed as a structurally integrated nanocomposite surfacing layer for composites. This novel sensor system enables the detection of strain in all directions using a single nanocomposite sensor, while simultaneously measuring temperature to isolate its effects. Experimental validation demonstrated that the sensor accurately measured the full in-plane strain tensor under tensile loading, closely matching the output of a 3-element strain gauge rosette. It also achieved high temperature sensing accuracy, with a maximum error of just 0.3%. By maintaining reliable strain and temperature measurement capabilities while simplifying system architecture, this CNT-based sensor system offers a promising solution for efficient and multifunctional SHM in aerospace and other advanced applications.

1 INTRODUCTION

Advanced composite materials have become widely adopted in engineering applications due to their high mechanical performance and low density [1,2]. In the aerospace industry, where minimizing structural weight is of paramount importance, fiber-reinforced polymer (FRP) composites are increasingly replacing conventional metals in primary load-bearing structures [3]. However, the heterogeneous composition of FRP—comprising distinct fiber and matrix phases—leads to more complex failure mechanisms than those observed in metallic structures [4,5]. This complexity, which includes failure modes such as matrix cracking, delamination, and fiber breakage, complicates accurate failure prediction [6]. As a result, structural health monitoring (SHM) plays a more critical role in composites than in metals, enhancing structural reliability and life-cycle management. Moreover, the inherently brittle characteristic of FRP composites makes early damage detection essential to mitigate degradation and prevent failure. Real-time SHM technologies capable of identifying damage at its onset are vital for reducing maintenance costs and avoiding catastrophic events. Although non-destructive inspection (NDI) methods such as ultrasonics, acoustic emission, and infrared thermography have shown effectiveness [7,8], their applicability to in-service structures—such as aircraft during operation—is limited [8].

Real-time SHM systems operate by tracking physical parameters through permanently embedded sensors. Strain is one of the most informative parameters, directly reflecting deformation and potential damage under load. Metallic strain gauges are commonly used in traditional SHM systems due to their low cost and ease of integration [9]. Fiber Bragg grating (FBG) sensors, embedded in composite laminates, have also gained popularity in aerospace structures for their high-resolution strain monitoring and minimal intrusion [3,10–14]. However, both metallic and FBG sensors are inherently unidirectional, measuring strain along a single axis [10,15]. To capture full in-plane strain states, at least three sensors oriented in different directions are required. Furthermore, their sensitivity to temperature necessitates an

additional sensor, such as a thermocouple, for thermal compensation, which increases system complexity and sensor count. In wired SHM systems, sensor cabling alone can constitute over 75% of the total installation time and around 25% of the system cost [16].

Carbon nanotube (CNT)-based nanocomposite sensors have attracted increasing interest due to their high conductivity and low weight since their discovery [17]. When dispersed into polymers, conductive nanofillers like CNTs yield nanocomposites with piezoresistive properties. Their electrical response can be tuned through material composition and filler ratio, enabling applications in both structural strain monitoring [18–24] and flexible wearable sensors [17,25–27]. Moreover, nanocomposite sensors possess an omnidirectional piezoresistive characteristic [28–31], a key feature that can be utilized to simplify the SHM systems.

Despite these advantages, the development of multi-directional nanocomposite sensors remains limited. Most studies emphasize high sensitivity and flexibility, often overlooking the importance of omnidirectional sensing. Typically, nanocomposite sensors utilize a two-probe method that only enables unidirectional measurement, restricting their multi-directional sensing potential. Furthermore, the coupled piezoresistive and thermoresistive characteristics of nanocomposites complicates accurate strain measurement under varying temperatures [32]. Most existing approaches isolate one variable while fixing the other, which limits practical implementation. Therefore, developing methods that allow simultaneous or decoupled measurement of strain and temperature is essential.

This study introduces a novel sensing system that enables simultaneous omnidirectional strain and temperature monitoring using a single nanocomposite sensor. The proposed approach incorporates two main innovations: (1) a sensing mechanism that accounts for both piezoresistive and thermoresistive characteristics to extract strain and temperature concurrently, and (2) a multi-directional measurement configuration that captures resistivity in four independent directions from a single sensor with reduced wiring complexity. These features allow for the formulation of four independent equations, enabling the simultaneous determination of the in-plane strain components (ε_x , ε_y , ε_{xy}) and temperature (T).

2 FRAMEWORK OF OMNIDIRECTIONAL STRAIN AND TEMPERATURE SENSING SYSTEM

This section outlines a semi-empirical framework for detecting omnidirectional strain and temperature using a nanocomposite sensor. Initially, a conduction model incorporating both piezoresistive and thermoresistive behaviors of the nanocomposite is introduced and experimentally validated within typical strain and temperature ranges of composite structures. A multi-directional resistivity measurement method is then presented to exploit the sensor's omnidirectional sensitivity. Finally, a system of equations based on the validated conduction model is formulated, enabling the estimation of in-plane strain tensor components and temperature from four electrical properties measurements.

2.1 Conduction model of omnidirectional nanocomposite sensor

Several conduction mechanisms, including tunneling [33] and hopping [34], have been considered for nanocomposite sensing. Among them, the fluctuation-induced tunneling conduction (FITC) model was selected due to its strong correlation with the resistivity behavior of CNT networks under varying strain and temperature conditions [35–38]. The FITC model describes resistivity as a function of temperature affecting tunneling probability, as follows [35]:

$$\rho = \rho_0 \cdot \exp\left(\frac{T_b}{T + T_0}\right) \quad (1)$$

, where ρ is the resistivity, ρ_0 is empirical resistivity constant, T_b is the energy required to transport an electron through the tunneling gap, T is the temperature of the nanocomposite, and T_0 is the temperature at which thermally activated voltage is generated. T_b and T_0 are empirically determined by examining the temperature variation in the zero-strain resistivity. Furthermore, the model can be extended by incorporating normal strain, based on the relationship between the junction distance of conductive nanofillers and the occurrence of tunneling effects, as expressed below [36].

$$\rho = \rho(0, T_r) \cdot \exp\left(\frac{\varepsilon}{\lambda} + \frac{T_b \cdot \exp(dT_b/d\varepsilon \cdot \varepsilon)}{T + T_0 \cdot \exp(dT_0/d\varepsilon \cdot \varepsilon)} - \frac{T_b}{T_r + T_0}\right) \quad (2)$$

$\rho(0, T_r)$ is the resistivity at room temperature T_r (297 K) with zero strain, and λ is an empirical strain sensitivity constant. ε denotes the strain in the nanocomposite that aligns with the direction of resistivity. The derivatives of $dT_b/d\varepsilon$ and $dT_0/d\varepsilon$ with respect to strain are approximated as $1.48 \cdot T_b$ and $0.020 \cdot T_0$ based on the assumption of image-force corrected rectangular potential barrier [36].

To assess the fit of the FITC model to the resistivity data of the nanocomposite under varying strain and temperature conditions, a CNT/epoxy nanocomposite sensor as fabricated and tested (fabrication details are in the Experimental section). The resistance of fabricated sensor was monitored with two-probe method under conditions of either varying strain or temperature, with the other variables held constant. By fitting the experimental data to determine the empirical parameters of Eq. 2, the resistance of the nanocomposite was accurately predicted with a strain parameter λ of 0.48 ($R^2 = 0.9941$), and temperature parameters T_b and T_0 of 118.92 K and 10.04 K, respectively ($R^2 = 0.9965$), as shown in Fig. 1a and b. The FITC model could accommodate strain values up to 0.63%, a range comparable to conventional FBG sensors (0.2% - 1.0%) [39-41]. Beyond 0.63% strain, a sudden increase in resistance was observed, suggesting potential morphological rearrangement in the CNT network or possible delamination of the Cu electrodes from the nanocomposite layer. Of note, a sharp resistance increase indicates possible network rearrangement or electrode delamination, consistent with prior findings [29]. The temperature parameters were fitted up to a maximum of 120°C, aligning with aerospace structure operating conditions [42].

2.2 Resistivity measurement method of nanocomposite sensor

Nanocomposite sensors have traditionally been constrained to detecting unidirectional strain due to limitations in their resistivity measurement methods. The two-probe method, which is the most commonly employed technique, measures resistivity along a single direction between a parallel pair of electrodes. This setup fails to utilize the potential for multidirectional strain detection inherent in nanocomposite materials. To address this limitation, the van der Pauw (vdP) method [43], a well-established four-probe technique for characterizing the resistivity of thin conductive films, was adopted for the nanocomposite sensor system. Among various extensions of the vdP method, the approach developed by Kleiza et al. enables determination of the resistivity tensor in anisotropic materials [44]. Their method allows for calculating the resistivity tensor components ($\rho_x, \rho_y, \rho_{xy}$) of a rectangular conductive medium equipped with four corner-mounted electrodes, as illustrated in Fig. 1c. These tensor elements are derived from four sets of resistance and current measurements (R_1, R_2, I_1, I_2), as demonstrated in Fig. 1d. The calculations are governed by the following equations:

$$\exp\left(-\frac{\pi \cdot d \cdot R_1}{\rho_{iso}}\right) + \exp\left(-\frac{\pi \cdot d \cdot R_2}{\rho_{iso}}\right) = 1 \quad (3)$$

$$\rho_x = \frac{a}{b} \eta \frac{A_{\alpha,k}}{A_{\alpha,1-k}}, \quad \rho_y = \frac{b}{a} \eta \frac{A_{\alpha,1-k}}{A_{\alpha,k}}, \quad \rho_{xy} = -\eta \cos(\alpha\pi) \quad (4)$$

Here, d represents the thickness of the conductive layer, while a and b are the side lengths of the rectangular nanocomposite sample shown in Fig. 1c. ρ_{iso} is the determinant of resistivity tensor [45]. The parameters are defined as follows: $\alpha = 1/(1+I_1/I_2)$, $\eta = \rho_{iso}/\sin(\alpha\pi)$, $k = \exp(-\pi \cdot d \cdot R_1/\rho_{iso})$, and $A_{\alpha,k} = \int_0^1 |f_{\alpha,k}(q)| dq$ where $f_{\alpha,k}(q) = q^{\alpha-1} \cdot (1-q)^{-\alpha} \cdot (1-kq)^{\alpha-1}$. By employing the vdP method, the resistivity tensor of the nanocomposite can be comprehensively obtained using only four electrodes positioned on a single sensor. In contrast to conventional applications of the vdP method, which are typically restricted to static characterization of conductive materials, this study implements it in real time to monitor resistivity variations in the nanocomposite under dynamic strain and temperature conditions.

2.3 System of equations determining omnidirectional strain and temperature

Given the omnidirectional piezoresistive behavior of the nanocomposite, the FITC model (Eq. 1) can be generalized to any direction under the assumption that the material is homogeneous and isotropic. By substituting the resistivity measurements taken in four independent directions ($\theta_1, \theta_2, \theta_3, \theta_4$), obtained via the vdP method into the FITC model, the following system of nonlinear equations is established:

$$\rho_{\theta_i} = \rho(0, T_r) \cdot \exp\left(\frac{\varepsilon_{\theta_i}}{\lambda} + \frac{T_b \cdot \exp(dT_b/d\varepsilon \cdot \varepsilon_{\theta_i})}{T + T_0 \cdot \exp(dT_0/d\varepsilon \cdot \varepsilon_{\theta_i})} - \frac{T_b}{T_r + T_0}\right), \quad i = 1, 2, 3, 4 \quad (5)$$

Since the in-plane strain tensor can be fully described by strain components in three independent directions, ε_{θ_4} can be expressed as a function of $\varepsilon_{\theta_1}, \varepsilon_{\theta_2}$, and ε_{θ_3} . Consequently, the four unknowns, the in-plane strain tensor elements and temperature, can be simultaneously determined by solving this system of four independent equations. As summarized in Fig. 1e, the developed nanocomposite sensor system enables the theoretical estimation of both the full in-plane strain tensor and temperature using just four directional resistivity measurements obtained from a single sensor.

Although thermal expansion effects were not explicitly incorporated into this study, the strain measured by the sensor includes both mechanical and thermal contributions. Therefore, future work should aim to extend the FITC model to explicitly account for thermal strain. With this enhancement, the sensor system would be capable of fully decoupling temperature effects from mechanical strain, thereby improving the accuracy and reliability of multidimensional strain sensing.

Figure 1: □ Omnidirectional strain and temperature sensing system based on nanocomposite sensor. Representation of (a) piezoresistive and (b) thermoresistive characteristics of nanocomposite sensor using the Fluctuation Induced Tunneling Conduction (FITC) model. Schematic of (c) the van der Pauw method applied nanocomposite sensor and (d) four electrical property measurements for in-plane resistivity tensor calculation. (e) Flowchart of the in-plane strain and temperature sensing process.

3 EXPERIMENTAL

To validate the proposed omnidirectional strain and temperature sensing framework, experimental studies were conducted by comparing sensor outputs with reference data from conventional strain and temperature sensors. This section is organized into two subsections: fabrication of the nanocomposite sensor and the experimental setup for measurement using both the nanocomposite and conventional

sensors. The fabrication subsection details the materials and manufacturing process for constructing the CNT/epoxy nanocomposite sensing layer on the composite substrate. The subsequent subsection describes the real-time measurement setup used to record the four sensing parameters of the nanocomposite sensor, along with data acquisition from conventional sensors.

3.1 Materials and fabrication of nanocomposite

A carbon fiber-reinforced-polymer (CFRP), commonly used in aerospace structures, was chosen as the composite substrate for sensor installation. The CFRP laminates were fabricated using unidirectional carbon fiber-reinforced epoxy prepreg (MCP125NS, TB Carbon) with a layup sequence of $[0/90/45/-45]_{2s}$. The fabricated laminates were then cut to dimensions of 250 mm x 25 mm in accordance with ASTM D3039M standards for tensile testing. High-conductivity CNT buckypaper (MWCNTs, US Research Nanomaterials, Inc.), with a purity of 99.9%, a thickness of 50 μm , and an areal density of 30 gsm , was used as the piezoresistive material for the nanocomposite sensor. As shown in Fig. 2a, the CNT buckypaper was cut into square films of different dimensions (10 mm x 10 mm, 20 mm x 20 mm) using a scalpel to assess the size effect of the sensor. Then, the films were attached to the CFRP surface using an epoxy adhesive film (Loctite EA 9695K, Henkel), which infiltrates the CNT network to form a CNT/epoxy nanocomposite surfacing layer during curing. The CNT films were oriented not only at 90° in the tensile direction, but also at 120° for shear strain measurements (See the coordinate axis of the sensor illustrated in Fig. 1c). Four copper films, each 10 μm thick, were then connected to the corners of the buckypaper as electrodes for the vdP method using a one-part silver epoxy (EO-98HT, Hightemp Korea). The assembled specimens were vacuum bagged as shown in Fig. 2c and cured at 120°C for 1.5 h in a convection oven, forming CNT/epoxy nanocomposite layer on the CFRP laminates.

Figure 2: Fabrication of composite integrated carbon nanotube (CNT)/epoxy nanocomposite sensor. (a) Schematic illustration of the structure. (b) Surface image of CNT buckypaper from a scanning electron microscopy (SEM). (c) Manufacturing process of the sensor specimen. (d) Fabricated nanocomposite sensor specimen for tensile test. (e) Cross-section image of nanocomposite sensor using SEM. (f, g) Top and side view of fabricated nanocomposite sensor.

3.2 Measurement setup

The developed omnidirectional strain and temperature sensor system was experimentally validated under uniaxial tensile loading by comparing its measurements with data from conventional strain gauges and an infrared (IR) camera, as shown in Fig. 3. Real-time, automated four-probe resistivity measurements were conducted using a Keithley 2400 sourcemeter which is synchronized with a switch matrix (Keithley 3706A & 3730), enabling real-time measurements with a 0.1-second delay without the need for manual probe switching. Conventional strain data were obtained from metallic strain gauges (FRA 2-11, Tokyo Instruments) configured in a rosette layout to capture strain in three independent directions. These strain gauges were installed on the rear surface of each specimen and connected to a data acquisition system (cDAQ-9174 and NI-9237, National Instruments) with a sampling rate of 2 kHz.

Concurrently, surface temperature data of the nanocomposite sensor were captured using a FLIR A700 infrared camera.

Given that the vdP method assumes a homogeneously conductive layer, the calculated strain tensor reflects an averaged strain across the nanocomposite sensing region. To evaluate the impact of this spatial averaging, digital image correlation (DIC) analysis was performed using VIC 2D software (Correlated Solutions, Inc.). A speckle pattern was airbrushed onto the nanocomposite surface, and high-resolution images were acquired to assess the local strain field. Uniaxial tensile loading was applied using a universal testing machine (INSTRON 4482), while sinusoidal cyclic loads were applied via a servo-hydraulic testing system (INSTRON 1350) to examine dynamic sensing performance across varying frequencies and amplitudes. Each test configuration was repeated with five specimens to compute the average response and standard error.

To further evaluate the sensor's ability to simultaneously detect strain and temperature under varying thermal conditions, additional experiments were conducted. For stress-free conditions, specimens were placed on a programmable hot plate (HP-61A-2, Torrey Pines Scientific) and gradually heated, while both electrical resistance and surface temperature were monitored using the sourcemeter and IR camera, respectively. Under quasi-static tensile loading, external heating was provided via a heat gun, introducing simultaneous changes in strain and temperature. These tests were conducted to validate the sensor's real-time capability in decoupling strain and temperature for structural health monitoring (SHM) applications.

Figure 3: Experimental setup for the validation of nanocomposite sensor system. (a) Image of the real-time measurement setup, including the nanocomposite sensor and references (strain gauge, DIC analysis and IR camera) during the tensile test. (b) Schematic illustrating the validation process of the nanocomposite sensor system by comparing its measurement data with reference data.

4 Results and discussion

This section details the morphological characterization of the fabricated nanocomposite sensor and presents the experimental evaluation of its omnidirectional strain and temperature sensing performance under tensile loading. Performance validation was conducted by comparing the sensor's four outputs with reference measurements obtained from metallic strain gauges and an IR camera. Quasi-static tensile tests were used to assess the sensor's accuracy and operational range, while cyclic tensile tests evaluated its real-time monitoring capability. Additionally, the system's capacity to measure strain and temperature simultaneously under varying thermal conditions was examined both in unloaded states and during uniaxial tension.

4.1 Morphological analysis

Fig. 2b shows a scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image of the commercial MWCNT buckypaper,

revealing a randomly oriented, homogeneous CNT network. The nanotubes, with diameters ranging from 30 to 50 nm, form a nanoporous structure that allows epoxy resin to penetrate during oven curing [46,47]. This ensures complete infiltration of the epoxy into the CNT network without disrupting the random alignment, as confirmed in Fig. 2e. This morphology is critical because isotropic strain sensitivity has been associated with randomly dispersed CNTs [28,29,48], while aligned CNTs tend to produce anisotropic responses [31,49].

To verify the isotropic electrical properties of the buckypaper, resistivity tensor elements were measured using the vdp method. The off-diagonal component ρ_{xy} was approximately zero, and the anisotropy ratio—calculated as the ratio of ρ_x to ρ_y [50]—was calculated to be 0.9817 ± 0.0123 (mean \pm SE), indicating near-isotropic behavior. In contrast, aligned CNT films typically exhibit an anisotropy ratio of around 1.44 ± 0.19 [49]. Given this isotropy, a constant gauge factor λ_c can be uniformly applied in all directions in the FITC model.

Beyond electrical uniformity, the low thickness (i.e., $\sim 50 \mu\text{m}$) and areal density (i.e., 30 gsm) of CNT buckypaper allow it to be embedded into structural surfaces without significantly altering their shape or mass. Accordingly, a CNT/epoxy nanocomposite layer was successfully formed on the CFRP substrate, maintaining the integrity of its surface morphology (see Fig. 2g).

4.2 Omnidirectional strain and temperature monitoring performance under quasi-static tensile loading

Fig. 4 shows the results of quasi-static tensile tests, where the nanocomposite sensor's measurements were compared with those of strain gauges and an IR camera across a strain range of 0.18%. When oriented 90° to the loading axis, the sensor simultaneously captured the full in-plane strain tensor and temperature (Fig. 4a). It accurately recorded both axial tension and transverse compression due to the Poisson effect, with negligible shear strain. The temperature measurement was also highly precise, with a maximum error of only 0.03%.

Slight discrepancies in strain measurement arose from the temporal mismatch between individual electrical readings, due to sourcemeter switching delays. With a sampling time of ~ 2 seconds, the system showed some limitations in accuracy compared to conventional strain gauges. However, these could be mitigated by employing faster electrical measurement systems. Despite this, the nanocomposite sensor offers a significant advantage by combining multi-directional strain and temperature sensing into a single sensing layer.

When the sensor was rotated to 120° , it was subjected to shear strain, yet it still managed to resolve the strain tensor and temperature (Fig. 4b). Some loss in measurement accuracy was observed due to instability in electrical readings caused by sensor shape distortion under shear strain. This is attributed to the limitations of the vdp method, which assumes rectangular geometry; deformation distorts resistivity calculations. A more advanced version of the vdp method for parallelogram-shaped conductors [51] could address this issue, albeit with added complexity and the need for five probes.

Figure 4: Sensing performance of nanocomposite sensor system monitoring omnidirectional strain and temperature under quasi-static tensile loading. (a-b) Comparison of in-plane strain tensor

measurements with strain gauges and difference in temperature measurements between nanocomposite sensor and IR camera in tensile direction of (a) 90° and (b) 120° , respectively (Mean \pm SE). The error bands represent the standard error of the nanocomposite sensor specimens.

4.3 Size effect of nanocomposite sensor

As shown in Fig. 5a-b, sensor specimens of various sizes were subjected to tensile loading under the same conditions as those applied during the quasi-static tensile tests. The strain distribution across the composite surface was evaluated using DIC, as depicted in Fig. 5c-f. The strain patterns observed on the nanocomposite sensor surface were in close agreement with those on the surrounding composite substrate, demonstrating that the sensor accurately reflects the structural surface strain. When the applied tensile strain reached 0.18%, approaching the upper boundary of the sensor's measurement capability, localized strain concentrations were observed near the sensor's electrode regions (Fig. 5e-f). This occurrence is attributed to the relatively poor adhesion of the copper electrodes compared to the structurally embedded CNT buckypaper within the epoxy matrix. Although the nanocomposite sensor's strain estimation based on the FITC model remains valid up to 0.63% strain (as indicated in Fig. 1a), premature delamination caused by weak electrode adhesion may arise before the irreversible rearrangement of the CNT network begins, ultimately limiting the operational strain range of the sensor. This limitation becomes especially critical in failure detection of composite structures, considering that the average yield strain of typical CFRP materials is approximately 1.4% [52]. To overcome this constraint, it is necessary to reinforce the nanocomposite sensor by enhancing the electrode materials and refining the sensor design to reduce strain concentration at the electrode boundaries, as identified through DIC analysis. Furthermore, no discernible differences in strain distribution were observed across nanocomposites of varying sizes, indicating that the presence of the nanocomposite layer does not influence the strain distribution on the epoxy surface layer, regardless of the sensor's size.

Fig. 5 g-h present a comparison between the strain data acquired from the nanocomposite sensor and the average surface strain measured via DIC over the sensor region. The nanocomposite region is outlined with white dashed lines in Fig. 5 c-f, excluding the electrode regions, which are marked with black dashed lines. The sensor system calculates an effective strain tensor by averaging the non-uniform strain field within the nanocomposite layer. This outcome arises from the inherent averaging characteristic of the vdP method, which interprets a heterogeneous resistivity distribution as an equivalent uniform resistivity field [53]. As a result, the piezoresistive nanocomposite sensor determines an effective strain tensor that represents the overall mechanical response of the sensing layer. Due to this averaging mechanism, even when the sensor area was increased by a factor of four, the calculated effective strain tensors under the same tensile conditions remained consistent between sensors, regardless of their dimensions. Moreover, in the quasi-uniform strain field induced during uniaxial tensile loading, the effective strain values measured by the nanocomposite sensor aligned closely with the mean strain over the entire nanocomposite region. This response is analogous to the behavior of conventional metallic strain gauges, where the measured strain corresponds to the average resistance change across the gauge section, with the gauge length defining the effective sensing area.

Figure 5: Size and averaging effect of strain measurements for nanocomposite sensor in different side dimensions. (a-b) Top view of nanocomposite sensors with different side lengths of 10 mm and 20 mm. (c-f) Strain distribution obtained by digital image correlation (DIC) in the tensile direction of 90°, under tensile strains of (c-d) 0.1% and (e-f) 0.18%. (g-h) Comparison of strain measurements from the nanocomposite sensors with the average strain of nanocomposite obtained via DIC. The error bands indicate the standard error of the nanocomposite sensor specimens.

4.4 Real-time monitoring performance of nanocomposite sensor

To assess dynamic performance, nanocomposite sensors (oriented 90° to the tensile axis) were preloaded by 0.4 mm (corresponding to strain of 0.55%) to avoid compression during cyclic loading, as they were specifically designed for tensile deformations. Following this pre-stretching, the specimens were then subjected to sinusoidal tension at two conditions: 0.025 Hz with 0.2 mm amplitude for 10 cycles, and 0.0125 Hz with 0.1 mm amplitude for 5 cycles. Measurements were recorded using the nanocomposite sensor, strain gauges, and an IR camera.

The real-time monitoring performance of the nanocomposite sensor specimens is shown in Fig. 6. The nanocomposite sensor reliably tracked all three in-plane strain components in agreement with the strain gauges (Fig. 6a), with average errors of 4.06% for the strain in the tensile direction (ϵ_y), 8.06% for the strain perpendicular to the tensile direction (ϵ_x), and approximately zero for the shear strain (ϵ_{xy}). The average strain error of the nanocomposite sensor is comparable to the reported average measurement errors of FBG sensors embedded in wind turbine blades, which are within 2.25% [54]. Future improvements should aim to enhance measurement accuracy to match that of conventional sensors by refining the calibration of strain and temperature sensitivities or by increasing the sensor's sampling rate. Nevertheless, the nanocomposite sensor maintained a low relative standard error in strain measurements, with a maximum value of 4.68%, demonstrating consistent real-time monitoring performance in all samples.

In addition to strain, the nanocomposite sensor also exhibited precise real-time temperature sensing, with a maximum deviation of only 0.203% from IR camera readings (see Fig. 6b). This accuracy indicates the sensor's ability to successfully decouple thermal effects from piezoresistive responses during dynamic loading. Notably, the temperature error from the nanocomposite sensor showed cyclic fluctuations aligned with the frequency of the applied mechanical loading, particularly at higher frequencies. These periodic variations were not observed in the IR camera data, as illustrated by the comparison in Fig. 6c. A frequency-domain analysis using fast Fourier transform (FFT) revealed distinct peaks at the loading frequencies (0.025 Hz and 0.0125 Hz) in the nanocomposite sensor data, while no such peaks were present in the IR camera data. Since the FITC model concurrently resolves both strain and temperature from the composite's resistive response, calibration mismatches in strain sensitivity may contribute to residual temperature errors, generating synchronized variations in both strain and temperature outputs. As a result, although strain changes are the dominant factor influencing resistivity during loading, minor cyclic variations in temperature data also emerged. Despite these fluctuations, the nanocomposite sensor achieved close agreement with reference sensors, affirming its capability for simultaneous strain and temperature monitoring.

Figure 6: Real-time monitoring performance of nanocomposite sensor system under cyclic tensile loading (Mean \pm SE). (a) Comparison of in-plane strain measurements with strain gauges. (b) Difference in temperature measurements between nanocomposite sensor and IR camera. The error bands represent the standard error of the nanocomposite sensor specimens. (c) Comparison of temperature measurements between one of the nanocomposite sensor and IR camera.

While the previous section focused on validation under room temperature with minor thermal variations, Fig. 7 evaluates the sensor's performance under substantial temperature changes induced by external heating. When the sensor's temperature increased by more than 30 K due to a heated plate without mechanical loading, the nanocomposite sensor measured temperature with less than 1% error, and strain readings remained near zero, as shown in Fig. 7a. Since the strain parameter in the FITC model is the sum of mechanical strain and thermal strain, a slight increase in strain measurements was observed in the stress-free condition due to the positive thermal expansion coefficient in the CFRP substrate. However, the strain in the x-direction increased less than in the y-direction unless the substrate was a quasi-isotropic laminate, indicating the presence of errors in strain calculations. As discussed in the cyclic tension test, this mismatch in temperature sensitivity is reflected in the measurement error of strain tensor elements, arising from coupled strain-temperature estimation in the FITC framework.

When convective heating was applied to the nanocomposite sensor during quasi-static tensile loading under the same conditions as depicted in Fig. 4b, the sensor system successfully tracked changes in both strain tensor components and temperature, thereby confirming the decoupling capability between piezoresistive and thermoresistive effects. The heater was activated while the tensile strain ranged between 0.03% and 0.06%, and again between 0.1% and 0.12%, as marked by the orange-shaded regions in the figure. During these heating intervals, strain measurement errors increased, particularly when the temperature ramp rate was relatively high; however, as the ramp rate decreased, the strain measurements closely realigned with the reference data. The rise in measurement error during rapid variations in strain or temperature is attributed to the low sampling rate caused by switching delays in electrical property acquisition. Despite this, the temperature readings from the nanocomposite sensor remained highly accurate, with a maximum deviation of just 1%.

Figure 7: Sensing performance of nanocomposite sensor system monitoring omnidirectional strain and temperature under varying temperature conditions. (a) Stress-free condition. (b) Quasi-static tensile loading.

5 Conclusions

The developed sensor system enables simultaneous monitoring of the in-plane strain tensor and temperature by utilizing the omnidirectional sensitivity of nanocomposites, based on a conduction model that incorporates both piezoresistivity and thermoresistivity, alongside a multi-directional resistivity measurement technique. This strategy significantly reduces the number of required sensors to 25% and cuts down the number of electrodes by 50%, needing only four electrodes per sensor. For system validation, CNT/epoxy nanocomposite sensing layers were fabricated directly onto CFRP substrates. These sensors act as structurally integrated layers on composite surfaces, offering smooth, paintable finishes similar to standard surfacing layers while enabling real-time detection of structural anomalies. SEM-based morphological characterization and resistivity testing verified that the nanocomposites exhibit isotropic piezoresistive characteristic, owing to their uniformly dispersed, randomly oriented CNT networks. Experimental evaluations confirmed the system's accuracy, with strain and temperature measurements closely matching those from traditional metallic strain gauges and IR cameras under both mechanical and thermal loading. Measurement accuracy was particularly high when shear deformation in the sensor was limited. Cyclic tensile tests validated the system's capability for simultaneous strain and temperature monitoring, supporting its application in real-time health monitoring of composite structures. Furthermore, strain distribution assessed via DIC showed that the strain tensors derived from the nanocomposite sensors correspond to the effective strain across the sensor area, regardless of sensor size, and mirrored the surface strain distribution of the structure. These results demonstrate the feasibility of simplifying SHM systems by embedding multi-directional strain and temperature sensing functionalities into a single sensing layer. Additionally, implementing appropriate insulation methods to mitigate electrical interference with the CFRP substrate may enable full structural integration of nanocomposite sensors within CFRP laminates, paving the way for multifunctional composite structures.

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